

Outcome-Based Learning through Apprenticeship Embedded Degree Programme to Meets the Gap of Employability

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Abstract

In the 21st-century era, skills are very important to solve any problems, problem-solving skills should be developed to solve the situational problem in our daily life. In the present degree programme, the curriculum which is practiced in schools, colleges, and universities are only develops the learners' knowledge not focused on skills. So problem-solving skills must be nurtured through curriculum not only theoretical but its hands-on experience through the training programme. Which makes the learners Apprenticeship and makes them capable to make the employable person. UGC has formulated these Guidelines for Higher Education Institutions to offer Apprenticeship/Internship embedded Degree Programme for embedding apprenticeship/internship in general degree programmes offered by the different kind of Universities. In the degree course curriculum should be such that can able to create the benefit of employment for the learner also government should to take the responsibilities to create the job opportunity of the learners. Objectives of this paper to proposed outcome-based learning through apprenticeship embedded degree programme (AEDP). Secondary data-based paper, Researcher collected data from different sources there are e-books reports, policies, Apprenticeship/ Internship Act's, websites, observation of various organization, journal articles, national and international articles published in local papers, etc. Apprenticeship programme enhance problem-solving skills and outcome-based learning for a new generation of learners.

Keywords: *Learning, Apprenticeship, employment, skills, Curriculum, Programme.*

Introduction

"If you are planning for a year, sow rice; if you are planning for a decade, plant trees; if you are planning for a lifetime educate people".

Chinese Proverb

In higher education (HE) curriculum should be more concentrated regarding liking to create skills base which directly helps for employability. An apprenticeship degree programme that is unique opportunities for all higher education learners to work-based degree and strategies

on embed employability too collaboratively. “We are wasting talent and this country's resources,” according to Grimwood. “As employers, we complain about the skills gap but we do not give people access to desirable jobs and careers.” in the recent era modernization of education rapidly changes the entire world. We are trying to enhance skills digitally as well as practically through internship and apprenticeship programme. A huge population in our country (India) already facing lots of problems due to lack of proper employability. If we want to resolve this problem we should be focused on an outcome-based skill-oriented degree programme. Outcome-based learning is that what we learning during the period of the course and its usability in the real ground. In the case of Switzerland apprenticeship programme is highly emphasis the education system, more than 70 percent student is participating various kind of apprenticeship programme, this country has a unique model in education, compulsory education on vocational / apprenticeship included. After training opportunities to apply workplace for the job. An apprenticeship programme is well established in Switzerland and Germany. Now India will be trying to established apprenticeship degrees for all students at the university level. Accordingly, UGC making the fresh graduates employment-ready with the necessary knowledge, competencies, and attitude, UGC has formulated these “**Guidelines for Higher Education Institutions to offer Apprenticeship/Internship embedded Degree Programme** for embedding apprenticeship/internship in general degree programmes offered by the different kind of Universities”.

Need and Significance of the Study:

Apprenticeship/internship has a great role in creating a link between higher education and the requirement process. This is the only way to develop skills and outcome-based learning for every learner. So UGC developed for UG degree programme for apprenticeship training at the university level. NEP-2020 already started to create opportunities for all universities. The teacher is a key element or aspect in the process of the education system and elevating the quality of education at a higher level of any organization. Before implementing any guidelines, rules and regulations must be necessary to check the suitability of every learner and how to work on outcome-based learning, and what will implementing a process in Indian societies. Large numbers of students are enrolment in a general degree programme in our India but after completing his or her study not getting a job this is the reality of unemployment. So that UGC trying to create links to various industries, NGOs, other sectors to reducing the gap of unemployment. AEDP (Apprenticeship Embedded Degree Programme) scheme will be provided outcome-based learning for every general degree course. Our great teachers monitoring the all-time teaching-learning process and achieve the objectives and goals of the education system. In the point of the career-building process, it will be a big emphasis on any educational guidelines. AEPD guideline stated that 20 credits for the UG course. Duration of Apprenticeship or internship will be followed one semester (six months) and provided 20 credits and this credit will be added to the final total credits. So the researcher studied the significance of this programme in the real ground.

The objective of the Study

- i) To study Outcome-based learning through an Apprenticeship embedded degree programme to meets the gap of employability.

Methodology of the Study

This present study is based on secondary data. Maximum relevant data has taken from different sources there are websites, census data 2001 and 2011 census report, journal articles, e-books reports, district statistical handbook and also National & international journal has taken as a source of data. That paper will give a brief description to study Outcome-based learning through an Apprenticeship embedded degree programme to meets the gap of employability.

Importance of Outcome-based learning

In recent digitalize decades, we need to understand SOL (Student learning outcomes) very much crucial for measurement in various ways. Here we concern about equality of teaching-learning process and apprenticeship of internship training programme. Here also student's teacher's attitudes and perceptions towards this apprenticeship embedded degree programme need to measurable understanding point of view. The General degree programme should be focused more on outcome learning for the linking opportunities of various job organizations. In higher education, learners are considered to enhance his or her performance depends on Institutional regulatory bodies.

Methods of application on OBL (Outcome Based Learning)

Different types of direct and indirect application methods will important for performance measurement of OBL, and it should be qualitative and quantitative parameters.

Direct methods

Indirect Methods

Here two application methods create play a great role for performance-based towards skill-based learners. Job-based education will be more necessary in curriculum and it's should be linked with various job sectors. Now in our India facing a lack of job or employment security after completing his or her graduate degree. So new policy tries to reduce the gap of employability through the apprenticeship programme. A successful Apprenticeship embedded degree programme creating a bridge between education and job or employment.

Definition of Employability

Need to understand the meaning of ‘Employability’ this word has the various definition given by different researchers, authors, educationist, etc. Employability includes a personal image, attitude, required skills, and aptitude.

“Employability is the capability to move self-sufficiently within the labor market to realize potential through sustainable employment” (Hillage & Pollard, 1998).

“Employability is the ability of the graduate to get a satisfying job” (Harvey, 2001).

Education and employment there are two separate things but it’s interrelated deeply. In the process of education as an input and output as employment. Our policies and government have the responsibility to, directly and indirectly, linking to enhance the economic growth of a nation. The government of any country has an emphasis on passing out of employable graduates to join a good job.

Needs of Employability

After completing a graduate degree from higher educational institutions, then everyone wants to join as an employer in any sector. Here the expectation is important to work for every job aspirant, not fulfilling expectation according to lack of opportunities. But the question is arise how completed he or graduates can fulfill their expectations? In a recent study 2016 by ASSOCHAM more or less 95 percent of graduates not getting a job according to their needs.

Input Education and Output Employment

Most challenging work for lots of economies to create a bridge between education and employment. A good policy can find out the main reason behind it and proper implementation in the real ground. According to ILO estimated that 80 million people are jobless and mostly belong to the young generation. In our India large number of students are doing general degree course like different language courses (Bengali, Panjabi, Santali, Gujrati, Karnnar, Odiya, Tamil, Assamese, etc.), different Social Science courses (History, Geography, Philosophy, Sociology, Psychology, Political Science, etc.) different Commerce courses (BBA, B.Com, CA, CS, LLB, etc.). After completing this type of course students are not getting a suitable job according to his or her needs and create unemployment. We are show data table bellow to proper understanding-

Table Data. 1.

State	Rate	State	Rate
Puducherry	75.5	Karnataka	43.2
Tamil Nadu	49.8	Odisha	41.2
Jharkhand	48.8	Uttar pradesh	23.8
Bihar	49.5	Maharashtra	21.5
Haryana	47.1	Andhara Pradesh	20.9
Tripura	46.6	Gujarat	20.5
West Bengal	17.4	Rajasthan	18.7
karala	17	Delhi	16.7
Goa	13.3	Madhya Pradesh	12.3
Assam	11	Uttarakhand	6.5
Meghalaya	10	Telangana	6.2
Chhattisgarh	3.4	Panjab	2.9
Skkim	2.3	Himachal Pradesh	2.2

Data source: Internet (April 2020)

Pic-1.The unemployment rate of India

Discussion

According to data and diagram show that unemployment rate is very bad in India. Sikkim, Punjab, Himachal Pradesh Uttarakhand, Telangana are unemployment rate average 3 percent and high unemployment rate Puducherry is 75.5 %. Also Tamil Nadu, Jharkhand, Bihar, Haryana, Karnataka are belong average unemployment rate. In recent employment rate dropped to 37.7 % in February compare to 39.4 % in 2019-2020. Here need to this study for the positive growth of employment rate. Out-come based learning through apprenticeship programme help to reduce gap of unemploymentability.

Table 2.Data source: Internet (April 2020)

Table Picture. 2

State	Rate
1999	17.75
2000	17.89
2001	17.91
2002	18.1
2003	18.11
2004	18.2
2005	18.3
2006	18.5
2007	18.11
2008	18.5
2009	19.67
2010	20.3
2011	20.84
2012	21.39
2013	21.59
2014	22.1
2015	22.34
2016	22.5
2017	22.72
2018	22.95
2019	23.34
2020	23.75

Discussion

Here we mention year 1999 to 2020 Unemployment rate in India. In the year 1999 was 17.75 % and year 2020 is 23.75 %. In total 20 year only rate increase approx. 6 %. Lack of various cause this was happened. But our government policies trying to more increase various way.

Employability is an outcome of the higher education system it belongs from any streams technical or general. Higher education curriculum should be more focused on ground-level job requirement skills as well as satisfaction labels of employers. Acquisition of outcome-based learning, soft skills increase through apprenticeship degree program programme. Another previous skills programme launched by HRD minister Shri Prakash Javedekar provided an apprenticeship programme (SHREYAS) in the industrial field for the general degree graduates in 2019 through NAPS. This scheme enhances the employment rate for young graduate students during the apprenticeship training stipend provided.

Scheme for Higher Education Youth in Apprenticeship and Skills programme also provided opportunities for general degree courses or non-technical students promote integral education and direct linked towards industrial sector jobs. In July 2020 UGC also another guideline for the general degree embedded apprenticeship programme to reduce and create link various industrial sectors, NGOs, and other sectors.

Outcome-based learning for Developing Employability

Higher education is the main path for developing nations through enhancing skills for employment. Whether students can enroll in any academic discipline needs to develop job-oriented scope according to expectation. The 12th five-year plan more emphasizes skills-based education and outcome-based learning in higher education. Apprenticeship training should be integrated learning opportunities for every learner. Outcome-based learning for Developing Employability through

Enhance the Positive Image

Through Apprenticeship embedded degree training programme learners create his or her image accordingly societies need then its works for self as well as economic growth.

Practice Behavior in Ethical ways

The apprenticeship programme for a general degree should be developed self-behavioral practices on depending on the ethical way. Understand the main context of a relationship between skills and employability.

Effectively Communication skills

Communication skills are most important for every job sector, proper communication skills enlarge your ability to work, enhance your perfection as well as your security of job satisfaction. This training will develop your ability to speak about your work.

Work Attitudes

Ability to learn can be developed positive attitudes of work and apprenticeship embedded degree programme will help towards work positive attitudes effectively.

Learn to Cooperation

Here cooperation is another important word for any organization, healthy cooperation, healthy cooperation plays a vital role in lifetime learning, and through the training, process learners can enrich that skills.

Responsibility

Any kind of Responsibility is a big issue for a particular job. Responsibility enhances our proficiency of skills so that outcome of learning learns to proper handy responsibility skills.

Apprenticeship embedded degree programme has taken Initiatives in Higher Education in India as link employability

OBL is one objective in this guideline to maintain the usability of the programme. A general degree program unable to direct link without apprenticeship training. Universities can build

your infrastructure and create a cooperation link between institutions and job organizations. This training more emphasis on

- a) Skill-based education in higher education it's more focused on career-oriented education will clear direction.
- b) Ready to join general degree courses.
- c) Get feedback response frequently.
- d) Proper credit system during semester
- e) More focused on Demonstration and practices.
- f) Develop yourself skills-based.
- g) Develop habit towards the requirement of Job.
- h) Promote engagement towards a traditional degree programme.
- i) Enhance more subject-specific knowledge.

Conclusion

The expected outcome of higher education in employability for the overall development of societies. Apprenticeship degree programme training is a very great initiative for the general degree programme learners, through this kind of apprenticeship learners should be developed and enhance subjective knowledge with practical experience. Learners can understand hand on knowledge as well as experiences through many opportunities from the various Industries, NGOs, and others sectors. But remember other things proper Implementation is most required for the all Universities to carry out this programme. After gained this training learners can develop self-discipline, knowledge to work with teamwork, and enthusiasm. The gap of the link between a general degree programme and employment should be reduced vice versa learners can also understand the different working opportunities for their.

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